

MICROMECHANICAL MODELLING OF Ti MMCS SUBJECTED TO TRANSVERSE TENSILE LOADING

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SUMMARY: A micromodelling analysis of unidirectionally reinforced Ti-6-4/SM1140+ subjected to transverse tensile loading has been performed using finite element methods. The composite is assumed to be infinite and regular, with either hexagonal or rectangular arrays of fibres in an elastic-plastic matrix. Unit cell models are applied in this analysis. The factors affecting transverse properties of the composites such as thermal residual stresses caused by cooling from the composite processing temperature, assumed fibre-matrix interface condition, fibre volume fraction, fibre spacing, and test temperature are discussed. There is a good agreement between FE analysis results and experimental measurements for transverse tensile behaviour of the composite Ti-6-4/SM1140+ with different fibre volume fractions and different fibre spacing ratios. The implication of these modelling studies to the design of components containing fibre-reinforced region is addressed.

KEYWORDS: finite element method, titanium matrix composites, unit cell model, silicon carbide fibres, transverse mechanical behaviour, and transverse tensile loading.

INTRODUCTION

With the development of Ti/SiC composites and for potential applications, the transverse properties of unidirectional continuous reinforced composites have received considerable attention. For instance, the transverse loading capability of the metal matrix composite (MMC) model being under consideration by Rolls-Royce plc. is of interest since maximum principal radial stress level could be one design limitation [1]. Also experimental work [2] has shown the transverse delamination failure of a clad MMC. Additionally finite element (FE) analysis has shown that transverse stresses are present in cracked clad titanium matrix composite (Ti MMC) testpieces, even when they are subjected to longitudinal loading [3]. Therefore it is important to understand the response of this MMC to transverse stresses. In spite of many studies on the transverse behaviour of Ti MMCs, there is little available data on the experimental and FE analyses of transverse behaviour of MMCs reinforced with DERA (Defence Evaluation Research Agency) Sigma fibres such as Ti-6-4/SM1140+. Based on the transverse tensile experimental data for Ti-6-4/SM1140+ [4-5], FE analysis of transverse properties in Ti MMCs has been carried out in this present work.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Material Properties

The composite considered in this work is Ti-6Al-4V unidirectionally reinforced with continuous Sigma fibres SM1140+ produced by DERA. The fibre is assumed to be isotropic, elastic and homogeneous with temperature independent properties [6-7]. The fibre diameter is 100 μm and various volume fractions have been investigated here: 35, 33, 31, 21 and 12%. The Ti-6Al-4V matrix is also assumed to be isotropic and homogeneous, but with temperature-dependent elastic-plastic properties. The plasticity is introduced by the von Mises yield criterion. Isotropic linear hardening is introduced at 20°C from the yield stress of 938 to 1000 MPa at a plastic strain of 0.024 [3]. The Prandtl-Reuss associated flow rule is used for plastic deformation. The stress free temperature of 570°C has been used in the present work [3]. Thus the FE analysis considers thermal residual stresses caused by cooling from a temperature of 570°C to a temperature of 20°C.

Finite Element Models

The composite is assumed to be reinforced with an infinite and regular, either hexagonal or rectangular array of fibres as shown in Fig. 1. Two-dimensional unit cell models of those arrays are used to model composite micromechanical properties with ABAQUS (a general-purpose non-linear finite element analysis program) [8-9]. Two-dimensional generalised plane strain elements are employed. Thermal loads are applied under the assumption that the temperature is uniform through the composite. The transverse load σ_x is applied in the x-direction as shown in Fig. 1. A fibre spacing ratio is defined by $R = b/c$ and $0.5b/c$ for the rectangular and the hexagonal fibre packing models respectively. Weak bonding between fibre and matrix is considered in this analysis and the interface is modelled as a contact surface by using small sliding interface elements in ABAQUS [9]. Stresses that can be transferred between fibre and matrix are normal compressive stresses and shear stresses via a Coulomb friction law. Generally, the first load applied to the composite is the thermal load imposed during the cooling procedure from a temperature of 570°C to a temperature of 20°C. After cooling from these temperatures, transverse mechanical loading is applied to the composite at a temperature of 20°C. For special cases different cooling procedures are considered such as from a temperature of 570°C to temperatures of 450 and 300°C.

Fig. 1 Regular periodic fibre packing arrangements and finite element analysis unit cells.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thermal Residual Stresses

There is little difference in stress distributions between the states of residual stress predicted by the rectangular and hexagonal fibre packing models. The FE results show that there is a compressive radial stress in the matrix at the fibre-matrix interface. For the composite with a fibre volume fraction of 33% and with a fibre spacing ratio of 1.2 the maximum radial compressive stress occurring in the matrix at the fibre-matrix interface after the cooling process is 293 MPa as shown Fig. 2. The residual compressive stresses induced at the interface between fibre and matrix contribute to the transverse mechanical behaviour of the composite because interface separation occurs only after the mechanical load overcomes these compressive stresses. Effect of residual stresses on the separation of the interface between fibre and matrix are thus very important.

Fig. 2 Residual stresses in 1-direction at room temperature after cooling from a temperature of 570°C ($V_f = 33\%$, $R = 1.2$, weak interface bonding (friction coefficient = 0.3), and hexagonal fibre packing model).

Transverse Mechanical Loading Behaviour

Despite the differences of the composites (such as in values of V_f and R) the overall stress-strain responses of all composites used in this study to transverse tensile loading can be roughly divided into the following four regions as shown in Fig. 3: (I) initial linear region, this region represents the elastic deformation of the composite; (II) transition (interface damage) region, it covers a range of interface damage from the start of interface slip to the separation occurring; (III) quasi-linear region, it is the region between the initial damage of the interface and yielding of the matrix. It is called a quasi-linear region due to the stress-strain curve in this region appearing to be approximately linear. The elastic deformation of the

matrix plays an important role in this region. The curve at this stage appears to be not really linear because the knee associated with the damage of the interface does not mean full separation of the interface. The damage of the interface continues to develop gradually until the separation the interface between fibre and matrix occurs over a major part of the interface; and (IV) non-linear region, The non-linear region represents the range between the start of matrix yielding and final failure. Plastic deformation of the matrix will contribute to this region. The average stress-strain responses predicted by FE analysis agree closely with the test results such as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 3 Average transverse stress-strain responses of the composites based on a weak interface (friction coefficient = 0.3) and hexagonal fibre packing model.

Fig. 4 Average transverse stress-strain responses of the composites with different fibre packing models predicted by FEM, which are compared with experimental results [5].

Effects of the Fibre-Matrix Interface on Transverse Mechanical Behaviour of TMCs

Some experimental results [10] suggest that there is a maximum shear stress of approximately 100 MPa at the interface between the fibre and the matrix for Ti-6-4/SM1140+, and the FE analysis in present research predicted a maximum residual compressive radial stress of approximately 300 MPa at the interface for this composite. Therefore a weak interface with a friction coefficient of $\mu = 0.3$ was suggested for modelling this Ti-6-4/SM1140+ composite based simply on the relationship $\mu = \tau/F_N$ (where τ and F_N represent the shear and normal stresses respectively at the interface).

Effects of Fibre Volume Fraction and Fibre Spacing on Transverse Mechanical Behaviour of TMCs

Effects of fibre volume fraction on the transverse mechanical response have been studied based on the composites with various fibre volume fractions (i.e. $V_f = 10, 20, 30, 35$ and 40%). To facilitate observation of the effects of fibre volume fraction, a fixed fibre spacing ratio of $R = 1$ was chosen initially in this analysis. With an increase of fibre volume fraction from 10 to 40% the transverse stress-strain curves show that the initial elastic moduli increase, the separation of the interfaces between fibre and matrix start at lower stresses, and the slopes of the curves decrease markedly after separation of the interface begins, as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Average transverse stress-strain responses of the composites with various fibre volume fractions.

Less attention has been paid to the effect of fibre spacing on the transverse mechanical response of MMCs compared with the fibre volume fraction. For the composite with different fibre spacing (fibre spacing ratios $R = 1.0, 1.2, 1.4$ and 1.6 are assumed here) and assuming a single fibre volume fraction of 35%, a FE analysis of transverse mechanical responses has also been carried out. With an increase of the fibre spacing ratio, R , it is observed that the initial elastic moduli will increase slightly, the separation of the interface

will start at higher stresses and the slopes of the transverse stress-strain curves will increase considerably after the separation of the interface (see Fig. 6). It is also noted that when $R > 1.2$ initial damage of the interface starts at the middle nodes of the interface (i.e. at $\theta \approx 45^\circ$) in the unit cell model (and not at the lower right-hand corner node of the interface, at $\theta = 0^\circ$). The reason for a higher "knee" in the composite with larger fibre spacing ratio, R , is deduced to be that the residual stress distribution is changed considerably with increasing fibre spacing ratio, R . As the fibre spacing ratio, R , increases, the residual compressive stresses at the interface between the fibre and the matrix at $\theta = 0^\circ$ in the unit cell will increase markedly. As a result the fibre spacing of the composite will be an important factor affecting the transverse mechanical responses of MMCs especially for promoting damage of the interface.

Fig. 6 Average transverse stress-strain responses of the composites with various fibre spacing ratios.

Fig. 7 Average transverse stress-strain responses of the composites with a constant distance D of 0.2 mm between plies and for the square root of $(R/V_f) = 1.6$.

Furthermore it is noted that the distance D (as shown in Fig. 7) between two fibre plies or fibres within one ply in the direction perpendicular to the transverse loading direction is directly proportional to $(R/V_f)^{1/2}$. It is found that for composites with the same value of D (or $(R/V_f)^{1/2}$) very similar transverse stress-strain curves are produced, and the FE results of a group of composites with a constant D of 0.2 mm (or $(R/V_f)^{1/2} = 1.6$) is shown in Fig. 7. Also the transverse proof stress $\sigma_{0.2}$ of the composite appears to be directly proportional to $(R/V_f)^{1/2}$ as shown in Fig. 8. Thus D (or $(R/V_f)^{1/2}$) will combine the effects of both V_f and R and may be a critical factor controlling the transverse mechanical response of MMCs. With improvements in manufacture techniques control of the fibre spacing is now possible, and thus the fibre spacing may play an important role in the design of MMCs for the future.

Fig. 8 Transverse proof stress $\sigma_{0.2}$, versus $(R/V_f)^{1/2}$ for all composites used in this present analysis.

Effects of Test Temperature on Transverse Mechanical Behaviour of TMCs

Based on FE analyses of the composite under transverse mechanical loading at different temperatures such as at 20, 300 and 450°C (see Fig. 9), it is clear that there is a strong effect of test temperature on the transverse mechanical response of the composites. With an increase of test temperature from 20 to 300 and 450°C the initial elastic moduli decrease by 13 and 25%, damage to the interfaces between fibre and matrix will start at 50 and 91% lower applied stresses and the slope of the transverse stress-strain curves of the composites will decrease markedly. This is because of reduction of the contribution of thermal residual stresses with increasing test temperature to the transverse mechanical response of the composite.

Fig. 9 Average transverse stress-strain responses of the composites under transverse stresses at different temperatures.

CONCLUSIONS

- (1) Residual compressive radial stresses induced during simulated cooling of the composite increase the ability of the fibre-matrix interface to support a normal load, and thus make a contribution to the transverse behaviour of composite.
- (2) A weak interface model is suggested for the transverse modelling of the Ti-6-4/SM1140+ composite. There is a good agreement between FE analyses and experimental results for predictions of the transverse tensile properties of the Ti-6-4/SM1140+ composite.
- (3) Both fibre volume fraction and fibre spacing will significantly affect transverse tensile properties of the composite (Ti-6-4/SM1140+). Factors such as $(R/V_f)^{1/2}$ combine effects of both V_f and R and will be a controlling factor in the transverse tensile behaviour of MMCs.
- (4) With increasing test temperature both the initial elastic modulus and transverse stiffness decrease markedly, and the damage of the interface between fibre and matrix will start at a lower stress due to reduction of the contribution of thermal residual stresses to the transverse tensile behaviour of the composite.

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REFERENCES

1. Harrison, G. F., Morgan, B., Tranter, P. H. and Winstone, M. R., "Metal Matrix Composites - Analysis of Simple Testpieces and Model Components under Creep and Fatigue Loading", in AGARD Meeting on Characterisation of Fibre Reinforced Titanium Matrix Composites, September 1993, pp. 14-1~14-15.
2. Doel, T. J., Cardona, D. C. and Bowen, P., "Fatigue Crack Growth in Selectively Reinforced Titanium Metal Matrix Composites", *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 20, No. 1, 1998, pp. 35-50.
3. Wang, N., Cardona, D. C. and Bowen, P., "Finite-Element Analysis of Selectively SiC Fibre-Reinforced Titanium Composites", *Inter. J. of Fracture*, No. 75, 1996, pp. 137-155.
4. Dore, A. L., "Effects of Fibre Volume Fraction on Tensile Damage and Fatigue Crack Growth in Titanium Metal Matrix Composites", PhD thesis, The University of Birmingham, U. K., Feb., 1997.
5. Cotterill, P. J. and Bowen, P., "Transverse Properties of a Ti-6-4 Matrix/SiC Fibre Reinforced Composite under Monotonic and Cyclic Loading", *J. of Material Science*, Vol. 31, No. 22, 1996, pp. 5897-5905.
6. Zok, F. W., Du, Z. -Z. and Connell, S. J., "On the Development of Fatigue Failure Maps for Titanium Matrix Composites", *Materials Science and Engineering A200*, 1995, pp. 103-113.
7. Ding, W., "Modelling and Experimental Studies of Damage in Titanium Metal Matrix Composites", PhD thesis, The University of Birmingham, U. K., June, 1997.
8. ABAQUS Theory Manual, Version 5.4, 1994, ABAQUS, Hibbitt, Karlsson and Sorensen Inc..
9. ABAQUS User's Manual, Version 5.4, 1994, ABAQUS, Hibbitt, Karlsson and Sorensen Inc..
10. Miracle, D. B., Gundel, D. B. and Warriar, S., "Interfacial Structures for the Design of Fibre Reinforced Metal Matrix Composites", to appear in "Processing and Design Issues in High Temperature Materials", Stoloff, N. S. and Jones, R. H., Eds., TMS, Warrendale, PA, USA, 1996.